

**THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING
IN TEACHING WRITING RECOUNT TEXT**

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Abstract: This study was carried out to describe the implementation and the quality of project based learning in teaching writing recount text to tenth grader. A qualitative descriptive research design was employed in this study. This study involved 15 students from tenth grader of one Islamic private school in Gresik. The data was obtained from observation and writing test. Students should make a book compilation in a class project. The findings showed that the implementation and the quality of project based learning achieve very good. The percentage of the implementation of project based learning reached 89%. So, the project based learning could be categorized as well implemented. Moreover, the percentage of students' achievement which passed the standard reached 87%. So, the quality of the learning viewed from students' writing achievement is considered as have a very good quality.

INTRODUCTION

Recount text is a text to retell experiences in the past (Anderson, 1997). Writing recount text, therefore, is very important for students to master since it develops students' writing skill in delivering chronological information. This skill later, will be needed in higher education or in university. In writing recount text, students will deliver

information in the sequence of: the introduction, the sequences of information and the conclusion (Anderson, 1997). In more detail, orientation leads to general information such subjects, place and time, while sequence of events leads to chronological information from the first event to the last in series. Re-orientation leads students to give a conclusion for the whole information in a point (Anderson, 1997).

In Indonesian curriculum, Recount text was determined as a text genre and should be taught and learned in high school, specifically as a core and basic competence for the tenth graders. It is stated that students should be able to comprehend and compose simple oral and written recount text based on the social function, text structure and language features based on context (Ministry of Education Regulation No.59, 2014 about Core Competence and Basic Competence). Therefore, it is mandated for teachers to build students’ recount text writing skills.

However, some English teachers in Indonesia still consider writing as a skill which is not tested in the national examination (Hernawati, 2015). As a result, this decision would affect students’ skill in writing because students get limited writing allotment. This condition also depicted in the research by Pratomo (2014) who observed that the teacher provided limited writing opportunity. In addition to that, Pratomo (2014) also reported that the limited activity provided are demotivating and therefore, decrease students’ learning motivation.

Limited writing allotment and students’ low motivation are not the only challenges in writing classes in Indonesia. Larasati (2015) wrote that the learning strategy was ineffective since teachers implement the direct Indonesian-English translation method. As the effect, students get demotivated and could not develop their skill. These writing challenges then added to the negative perception of the students on writing makes

writing class, although important, but show little significance in improving students' skill (Chikita, Padmadewi, & Suarnajaya, 2013). Therefore, teachers need to provide more interesting activities, a contextual topic which is close to students' daily life and give motivation for students to improve their writing skill.

Due to the significance of recount text for students to master yet challenges both from the side of the students and the teachers were reported, urgent needs for a more effective instructional strategy is irrefutable. One of the solution in teaching writing recount text is to equip students with various sources of information students can get (Sciamarelli, 2010). Moreover, if the methodology applied in learning the recount text is project based learning, and that it is based on students' real life, Lystiana (2016) stated that it will help students to write better because students can relate it closely with the writing text and because students can share their idea, creativity and imagination. All in all, project based learning methodology may also resolve the challenge of students' boredom and low motivation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

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Different to the other learning methods which provide limited activity for students, project based learning is students-centered which provides more activities (Liao, ____). In the teaching writing, it means that students will get more writing allotment in the learning. It also allows students to discuss, plan and compose a project in their writing activity (Thitivesa, 2014). Moreover, Larasati (2014) stated that students will work in team and support each other in the project. Students will think more complex rather than writing a simple text in the learning. Thus, project based learning is considered as a learning strategy for teaching writing.

The researcher does not take all of the micro and macro skills given above. He will only take as he needs to achieve the standard of writing in the school and the national education. It is including the grammatical system (4), rhetorical forms and conventions of written discourse (7), communicative function of written text according to form

and purpose (8) and conveying links and connection between events (9). These criteria were also used by Pearson (2012) in Kentucky education department to assess writing. It includes the idea, organization, words choice and sentence structure.

Writing Performances

There are four categories of written performance which are captured from the range of written production (Brown, 2007). This will be used by teacher to decide the level of the writing produced by the students. Teacher will consider the target of the writing task by those performances. Those are listed as the followings:

A. Imitative

It is the basic and fundamental skill of writing. The students are focused on writing letters, words, punctuation and very brief sentences. At this level of performance, the writing form is the primary, while meaning and context is secondary concern.

B. Intensive

It also called as controlled writing. In the imitative writing, students focus on the vocabulary, spelling and other basics. Here students start the essential meaning of their writing where the context is considered. But they need to be guided as the beginner.

C. Responsive

While creating a sentence with single context and meaning, responding another meaning of writing seems like a higher level of writing communication. Students respond the context and produce the responding context. This level could reach the paragraphs composing. And strong meaning has been the attention.

D. Extensive

Extensive writing implies the management of writing kinds of text for all purpose. Students started to elaborate the idea systematically in the writing types, such as essay, project report, daily story or even a thesis. Purpose,

developing idea, organization and other specific aspects are being the focus in this level.

By those writing performances, researcher will only apply the extensive writing which presents higher target for the students to produce the writing. It also trains them to organize their writing independently, widely and chronologically based on their experience. In the process of the learning writing activity, extensive writing engages in the process of multiple drafts to achieve a final project (Brown, 2007). Thus, the extensive writing will be very suitable for the Project-Based Learning which is also process-oriented.

Moreover, the focus of extensive writing which is achieving purpose, developing idea, and organizing the writing will make students able to explore their selves. Supported by specific topic which is close to the students' daily live, students will be more help to develop their writing wider. Therefore, having a specific topic in extensive writing is very helpful in students' writing process.

Project-Based Learning Process

Project based learning can be understood as a learner-centered teaching approach which focuses on the process or efforts (Marwan, 2015). There are different steps of project-based learning in its development, but The George Lucas Educational Foundation (2005, cited in Larasati, 2015) gives a more detailed procedure of project-based learning which is appropriate for this study.

- a. Start with the essential question

This step is aimed to give the students essential question which leads the students to the project.

- b. Design a plan for the project

In this step, the teacher gives chance to the students to be involved in designing the project.

- c. Create a schedule

Following the previous step, the teacher and the students should discuss the time allotment in doing the project.

d. Monitor the students and the progress of the project

This step is the most crucial step which teacher should be a facilitator for the students’ project progress.

e. Assess the outcome

The assessment would be the teacher job as the students have been working during the project doing.

f. Evaluate the experience

The evaluation would be the last step of the project-based learning which the teacher and the students will evaluate the project they have done.

Recount Text

A Recount text is a type of oral or written text which purposed to retell the listener or readers about the past experiences, history or even activity report. It also requires orientation, the sequence of events and reorientation. We could find recount text in some fiction or non-fiction novel, biography or even dairy book.

Generic Structure

There are three points of text structure of recount text based on Mark and Kathy Anderson (1997 and 2003) which is used as the reference for many English learning textbooks. Those are:

1. Orientation

As one part of recount text, Orientation introduces the participants, place and time of the story. This part will gives background information to the reader about who, where and when is the story happened.

2. Events

This part of text describes the series of event that happened in the past. As we call it series, we may deliver it in sequence whether it is front, back or flashback. Or even we deliver it chronologically.

3. Reorientation

This last part states a conclusion and personal comment of the writer to the story. What they feel or think after the experience? We may also call this part as conclusion of the story. After all, this part is optional.

Language Features

1. Introducing personal participant: I, my group, my family
2. Using linking verb: was, were, saw
3. Using action verb (past form): looked, went, changed, ran
4. Using simple past tenses: I went to the field, We ran from the buffalo
5. Using chronological conjunction: then, first, after that.

METHOD

The research design in this study is descriptive qualitative research. Ary, Jacobs and Sorensen (2010) stated that a qualitative research aims to understand a behavior concern for context and meaning. This research design is applied in order to describe the implementation of project based learning in teaching writing recount text to tenth graders. The researcher gives project based learning to one class as a treatment. The researcher then describes the implementation of the learning and the learning quality.

The data collected will be analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. Quantitative analysis will be used as supporting data, while the focus of this research is describing the implementation of the learning and the learning quality. This multiple types of analysis is possible in doing a qualitative research to engage more information in different forms (Creswell: 2012).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The lesson plan proposed by the researcher for implementing the project based learning was for four meetings. But in some condition of the school, the researcher could only do the project based learning in three meetings. The researcher then arranged the learning to be finished in three meetings. The researcher maximized the learning process to finish the project. He did not give additional examples of recount text as planned. He asked students to explore the recount text by themselves in the internet. So the information given by the researcher in the learning was very simple and limited. However, the students could achieve the standard of the learning and the learning was very well implemented.

In addition, this study proved that the implementation of project based learning in teaching writing recount text improve the writing skill, especially in the aspect of idea and organization. It showed by the average point in each aspect as follows.

Table 4.1 Students’ Point in Each Aspect

NO	NAMA	RUBRIC SCORE				POINT
		IDE	ORG	WD. CHO	STRC	
1	AR	4	3	3	3	13
2	AF	4	3	3	2	12
3	AM	4	3	3	2	12
4	FZ	4	3	4	3	14
5	JR	4	3	4	3	14
6	MASP	4	4	3	3	14
7	MAH	4	4	3	3	14
8	MAM	4	4	3	3	14
9	MFM	2	2	2	2	8
10	MSH	3	3	2	2	10
11	MTH	4	3	3	3	13
12	MA	3	3	3	3	12
13	PBS	4	3	3	3	13
14	SN	3	3	3	3	12
15	UM	3	3	3	3	12
TOTAL POINT		54	47	45	41	

AVERAGE POINT	3.6	3.1	3	2.7
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The table above presented that the average point of Idea reached 3.6, while the average point of organization reached 3.1. It proved that project based learning improved students writing skill especially in idea and organization of the text.

The Students Writing Achievement

Among 13 students who achieved the standard, there were 2 students who did not achieve the standard. They were sample 1 and sample 2. Generally, both students were not achieving the minimum words, poor of sentence structure, word choice and organization. The researcher told them some suggestion from their first writing, but they did not do significant improvement. Here are the details of their writings from the draft until the final writing.

Figure 4.7 Sample 1 of Student's draft

The student's writing had a complex problem including capitalization, punctuation, spelling, past form verb and the organization. He did not recognize the capitalization of the word "I", missed some spelling in the past form words, his organization of recount text was not complete because he missed the re-orientation.

Figure 4.8 Sample 1 of Students' Final Writing

After the revision, sample 1 only revised the grammatical mistakes and ignored the minimum word standard and organization. It was indicated that he did not master the simple past very well. So that he miss the spelling. He also lacked of using word typing software, so he missed the auto-capitalized feature. Moreover, sample 1 was typically passive in the learning activity by the teacher's observation.

Thus, the next researcher should make sure that all students learned the simple past before. Then recount text would be easier for them to learn. In the typing word project, the researcher should make sure that the students are able to operate the software and also remind them to pay attention to the capitalization. Furthermore, the researcher should pay attention to all students in the learning process, especially for the low motivated students.

Figure 4.9 Sample 2 of Students' draft

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Student’s sample 2 writing problem is similar to student’s sample 1 writing, but his writing is better. He missed some past form, organization and not translated words. He missed the irregular verb which has different form (forbid = forbade).

Figure 4.10 Sample 2 of Student’s Final Writing

Different to sample 1, in his final writing, sample 2 had a re-orientation in his writing, but the way of the story seems like jumping or skipped. Moreover, in

the first writing, He was indicated using a translation application in his writing. In addition, researcher should remind the students to not use the translation in their writing because it would ruin the structure of the text.

CONCLUSION

The result of the study is the project based learning implemented very well and the quality of the project based learning based on the students' writing achievement is considered to have a very good quality. The implementation of project based learning in teaching writing recount text for tenth graders is considered as very good. The implementation percentage of project based learning in teaching writing recount text is 89.3%. In addition, The quality of project based learning viewed from the students' writing achievement is considered to have a very good quality. The percentage of students' achievement reached 87%. Furthermore, The students' response towards the project based learning viewed from the last evaluation of project is good. Most of the students helped each other and were cooperative in doing the book project.

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